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Philip MODIANO

*International Expert (UK, London);
Convenor/curator of The Petit Society; Art Critic, Culturologist;
e-mail: pmodiano@orgperf.com*

John Louis Petit – Rediscovering An Overlooked Forerunner of Impressionism

Abstract. *John Louis Petit (JLP, or Petit) 1801–68 is one of the most important British artists whose work has had a huge influence on architecture. At the same time, both his work and individual pages of his biography are full of mysteries and unknown facts. This work is aimed at studying the creative heritage of John Louis Petit. The research is based on the study of published sources and scientific works, as well as art criticism analysis of Petit’s creativity. The author outlines the main aspects of his career and then assesses the ways his art is significant in the wider context of European art history of the mid-19th Century.*

Keywords: *John Louis Petit, pre-impressionism, British impressionism, British art, Petit’s creativity*

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МОДИАНО Филипп

*международный эксперт (Великобритания, Лондон);
руководитель/куратор Благотворительного общества Петита,
искусствовед, культуролог; e-mail: pmodiano@orgperf.com*

**Джон Луи Петит: новое открытие
малоизвестного предшественника
импрессионизма**

Джон Луи Петит (1801–1868 гг.) – один из важнейших британских художников, оказавший огромное влияние на архитектуру. Тем не менее, как его творчество, так и отдельные страницы его биографии, всё ещё полны загадок и неизвестных фактов. Целью данной работы является изучение творческого наследия Джона Луи Петита. Исследование основано на изучении опубликованных источников и научных работ, а также искусствоведческом анализе творчества Петита. Автор¹ описывает основные аспекты его творчества, а затем оценивает значимость его искусства в более широком контексте истории европейского искусства середины XIX века.

Ключевые слова: *Джон Луи Петит, преимпрессионизм, британский импрессионизм, британское искусство, творчество Петита*

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¹ Филипп Модiano – руководитель/куратор Благотворительного общества Дж.Л. Петита (с 2016 г.). Общество Петита существует с целью восстановления репутации и сохранения работ Джона Луи Петита (1801–1868), чьи работы считались утраченными до 1980-х и 1990-х гг. Ф. Модiano интересуется произведениями XIX в., пейзажами, художественными течениями Великобритании и Франции, импрессионизмом и предимпрессионизмом, неоготикой и архитектурной литературой XIX в. Является владельцем крупнейшей коллекции, насчитывающей более 1000 произведений искусства Дж.Л. Петита и его окружения, организует выставки, выступает с лекциями и ведёт исследовательскую работу.

John Louis Petit (JLP, or Petit) 1801–1868 (plate 1), was nationally famous in Victorian Britain for both his art and architectural writing, yet until recently had become practically forgotten in both fields. Sir Nikolaus Pevsner accorded him half a chapter in his summary of *Architectural Writers of the 19th Century*, but only includes one of his publications (Pevsner, 1972)²; while his 2005 entry in the *Oxford Dictionary of National Biography* is full of errors (Braithwaite, 2005)³. His recovery in Britain began with publications first in the *British Art Journal*⁴ (Simon, 2017). In 2017, and has now extended to exhibitions⁵, a symposium on his architectural approach⁶, and other activities. It is now appropriate that his achievements are acknowledged outside Britain because “*There has been nothing like this in the field of British Art for a very long time*” (Graham-Dixon, 2022)⁷.

Petit's work has received considerable attention in the scientific community. Thus, Philip Modiano, in a series of scholarly papers devoted to Petit, describes how his style developed over his life and career, paying particular attention to early groups of works that were hidden in sketchbooks until they were unearthed in the 1980s and 1990s. After considering Petit's unusual architectural motivations that drove his painting in these later years, Philip Modiano presents and analyzes a number of his late landscape works, supported by Petit's own comments on his art or art in general. The article highlights: the subject matter of Petit's work; his choice of real, everyday scenes and natural rather than "enhanced" or staged compositions, based on an unconventional understanding of "picturesque" for that time; his aims to realistically capture the "effect" of buildings or nature in different light, shadow and climate. Modiano calls Petit "a true progressive", meaning that he belongs to those currents that eventually led to the art of the twentieth century (Modiano, 2017, 2022). *A number of works examine Petit's work both in the context of general studies of Impressionism and from the point of view of its British movement (for example, Isaacson, 1990; Flint, 2016; Szatkowski, 2022).*

The obvious lack of research into Petit's work determined the purpose and relevance of this study.

Any work of art is inseparable from the artist's biographical background and environment. That is why Petit's creativity should be studied through the prism of his biography.

As the eldest son of a wealthy member of the landed Staffordshire gentry Petit never needed to earn a living, although he always sought useful occupation. After Eton and Cambridge, he followed in his father's footsteps by taking religious orders in 1826, and served as stipendiary curate in Lichfield for 2 years and then in the twin parishes of Bradfield and Mistley, Essex, for 6 years from 1828–34⁸.

² Sir Nikolaus Pevsner, *Some Architectural Writers of the Nineteenth Century*, pp. 95-100.

³ Guy Braithwaite, *Biography of Rev John Louis Petit*, *Oxford Dictionary of National Biography*, edition 2005, pp891; for example wrongly dating his church service see footnote 14.

⁴ *British Art Journal* vol XVIII No 2 pp40-50. This article includes material from this and a subsequent BAJ article updated with more recent research.

⁵ Lichfield Cathedral July 14th 2024 et seq; Staffordshire History Centre February 2025 et seq; Rutland County Museum Aug 23rd 2025 et seq.

⁶ Due September 27th 2025.

⁷ Endorsement by Andrew Graham-Dixon, art critic and broadcaster in the UK, from *JL Petit – Britain's Lost Pre-Impressionist* (RPS Publications, 2022).

⁸ Clergy of Church of England database. These differ from the Oxford DNB, op cit, which states that he served in Bradfield from 1840-48, not the case since he was living in Shropshire then and busy with his writing and speaking.

Reportedly he “showed an early talent for painting”⁹. Three albums exist from his student years in Cambridge, and several pictures remain from an album reportedly dated 1828. These are much simpler in character (pl. 2). Some pictures can be dated by their architectural features, for example Bakewell Church to around 1830 because of the absent spire which had fallen and was yet to be replaced (pl. 3). During the Bradfield years he adopted a distinctive darker palette that would continue to some extent until 1843. He also visited the Netherlands from Harwich (pl. 4), and drawings from there are the earliest known to have used in publications (pl. 5).

It is not known if Petit took lessons from an established watercolourist but Peter de Wint (1784–1849) and Samuel Prout (1783–1852) were strong early influences, the former for landscape and the latter for architecture. In both cases pictures exist from the same location and in the same style. Concerning Prout, there is evidence that they were acquainted and owned each others work (Petit, 1846, 2010)¹⁰. Petit praises Prout in his first book¹¹, and it was reported that Prout admired his work (Petit, 1846, 2010)¹². One can see Prout’s influence in Petit’s church drawings from the early 1830s in the choice of dramatic viewpoint and the limited palette. For example, a picture of Canterbury Cathedral undergoing reconstruction of the north-west tower which can be reliably dated to 1832 because the dismantling of the old tower had just begun¹³ (pl. 6). Prout’s influence is especially noticeable in the Low Country paintings from the early 1830s. Prout’s etchings from Flanders were published in 1833 and include similar views¹⁴. The differences between Petit and Prout are instructive (pl. 7 and 8). While Prout delivered rounded, sometimes even contrived, compositions, with carefully placed figures and secondary points of focus for the commercial market, Petit focuses entirely on the architecture and creates a different, but perhaps no less powerful effect.

From this earliest period, we also find Petit attracted to painting scenes in which no other artist of the time was interested: namely industrial views. Those in the neighbourhood of Wolverhampton were adjacent to his land holdings, but this does not seem to be a motivation. With a broader, whole of life view one sees a curiosity, and a captivation with the architectural impact of modern utilitarian structures (pl. 9 and 10). Pictures such as these are ‘exceptionally rare’¹⁵. Petit has

⁹ Albert Hartshorne, Obituary in *The Builder*, Iss. of Jan. 1869. Hartshorne was the son of a close friend of Petit, Charles Hartshorne, Antiquary, and also became editor of the *Archaeological Journal*.

¹⁰ ‘I remember being much struck with a remark made to me by Mr. Prout; namely, that the beauty of certain continental towers consists in the comparative plainness of their lower stages, while the interest of the building increases towards the top’ Rev J L Petit, *Principles of Gothic Architecture as applied to Ordinary Parish Churches*; Oxford, 1846, p.8. Two drawings of Petit descended in Prout’s family, and Petit exhibited Prout’s work on occasion.

¹¹ ‘The peculiar Flamboyant of the town hall demands notice; this building is familiar to all who are acquainted (as who is not ?) with Mr. Prout’s drawings’. Rev. J. L. Petit, *Remarks*, Vol. 2, p. 163. Speaking of the Stadhuis Ghent, see the images pl. 7 and 8.

¹² Prout is reported to have said that ‘If Mr. Petit was forced to resort to painting as a profession, he would excel even myself’. Reported in a review of a Fine Art Exhibition of watercolours in the *Gloucester Echo* of 1886.

¹³ ‘Sept. 3. 1832 – The ceremony of laying the first stone of the new tower took place’ *The Gentlemen’s Magazine*, Vol. 152.

¹⁴ Samuel Prout, *Etchings from Flanders, Germany and the Low Countries*; a copy of which is in the British Museum, as are some of the original watercolours.

been said to have ‘created a tradition of industrial images of the Black Country and beyond’.

After resigning his parish in September 1834, he moved back to the west Midlands, initially living at Shifnal in Shropshire, and in the following years sketched widely in the UK, including some of those that were to be used in his first publication, *Remarks on Church Architecture* (Remarks), published in 1841. Tixall Gateway, north of Stafford, is the first illustration apart from the frontspiece and seems to have been chosen to mark his entrance into the architectural debates of the day, although the watercolour is likely to date from several years earlier (pl. 11).

A few watercolours can be reliably dated either because they are the basis of illustrations in his book, or because they show a church prior to restoration, such as St Mary’s Stafford (pl. 12) showing the clerestory and flat roof of the south transept (on the right of the building), the subject of the dispute with Gilbert Scott¹⁶ (Webster, 2001). Here we still see the influence of Prout, yet Petit maintains his greater focus on the church while increasing the colour and breadth of composition. A later example, Ashbourne Church Derbyshire, which he painted at least 6 times, circa 1838, shows further development in style (pl. 13)

By the latter part of the 1830s he was drawing prolifically, and by no means only churches. It is always rare to find dates on Petit’s early work, however, a group of over 40 watercolours, from central Derbyshire, mainly landscapes, are all dated from March to May 1838. Some show particular experimentation with trees and colour (pl. 14), and these would then lead on to even more colourful work, on the continent, in 1838–40 and build a foundation for his impressionistic style which he would continue to develop there.

Petit’s first book – *Remarks on Church architecture* (Remarks) appeared in 1841, in two volumes with 278 illustrations, of which just over 100 were of UK churches and around 90 from France (the rest from Italy, Germany, Belgium and Holland and Switzerland) The illustrations themselves were mostly produced by Petit and based on watercolours almost all of which¹⁷, Petit had also taken himself (Petit, 1841). Concerning the illustrations, he explains:

“I have done my best to set before the reader a sufficient variety, both in form and composition, to prove to him how wide a range can be taken by architects....to be confined neither to one country, nor one age, nor one scale of importance; to comprise not only finished and elaborate specimens, but the roughest and plainest chapels or village churches, many of which, on account of their unpretending beauty, attained solely by proportion, are invaluable” (Petit, 1841)¹⁸.

Apart from a few from the Netherlands mentioned above and taken earlier, the watercolours from other countries for this book were presumably done from late 1838 to 1840, although this needs confirmation. They show a further development of Petit’s style and are some of the richest in colour, and lightest, from his entire career (pl. 15.) Occasional landscapes from these trips are similarly vibrant (pl. 16).

¹⁵ Dr. M. Dick OBE, Chairman of the Black Country Society, quoted from *The J.L. Petit Ser. 2. Impressions of Industry* (RPS Publications, 2025), p.1.

¹⁶ *A Church as it Should Be*, Webster and Elliot, 2001. Op cit, ch. 12 and ch. 8.

¹⁷ Rev J. L. Petit, *Remarks*, op cit, ‘I may say that in almost every case they are from drawings taken on the spot, either by myself, or by friends whose eye and hand I would rather trust than my own’. Preface p. viii.

¹⁸ *ibid*, Preface p. vi.

The book attracted fulsome praise in most reviews¹⁹, and vitriolic criticism from *The Ecclesiologist*. Without going into too much detail, for the purpose of this article I shall mention three main points of dispute to illustrate the depth of the conflict. These concerned: the role of beauty in church architecture, the use of international models, and whether there was one correct style (14th century Gothic) which had to be copied for restoration or for new churches.

On the first: '...we are sorry to observe that there [is] no reference whatever to a higher standard than that of mere taste in church-building, which is treated quite as a matter of trade, convenience, caprice, or of arbitrary arrangement, instead of one that has ever involved and been influenced by the most unvarying and exalted principles'²⁰. The principles that *The Ecclesiologist* refers to being those that they sought to dictate.

Concerning the use of international models: '...nor does it seem at all necessary to have recourse to churches which very few may have the opportunity of visiting...unless it be the wish that our own most pure and beautiful models so admirably adapted to the genius of our Church, our nation, and our climate, should be superseded by pagan varieties imported...'²¹.

And, on copyism, where Petit says "'surely it would be better to attempt maturing a style that might be rendered correct and pleasing: than to continue in the imitation of models...owing their principal value to a charm that we cannot impart to our copies...that of antiquity'" *The Ecclesiologist* answered 'We can only observe that we differ totally from Mr. Petit on every single point here alleged by him'²². They refused to publish his letters of rebuttal, and he published them himself in 1843²³.

Such rude language in print was almost unheard of (though by no means so in 20th Century architectural disputes). It is important because it appears to have marked the moment when his career became set. Nowadays we would probably agree with Petit on each point, but then he was fighting a tide of fashion. From this time on his energy seemed to be devoted to his speaking and writing, and his painting talent became a tool he used to distinguish himself from the many other gentlemen with archaeological or ecclesiological interests. Together with other like minded intellectuals the Archaeological Institute (AI), later Royal, was founded in 1844, with their organ *The Archaeological Journal*, under the leadership of Albert Way, the Director of the Society for Antiquaries; and the Architectural Institute, later RIBA started a little earlier, which subsequently sponsored the Architectural Exhibition Society and Architectural Publications Society. Primarily through these avenues Petit published over 40 separate articles and speeches from 1844 on, nearly all of which reprise one or more of the above three main points of dispute²⁴.

Intense artistic activity continued every year, until his death in December 1868. However, now his art was being exhibited at public lectures, in quantity, and

¹⁹ For example, *The Gentleman's Magazine*, Mar 1842, p. 288-296; *The British Critic and Quarterly Theological review*, Jan. 1842, Vol. 31, p. 244-254.

²⁰ *The Ecclesiologist*, March 1842, p. 91.

²¹ *ibid*, p. 92.

²² *ibid*, p. 93.

²³ Published 15 page letter addressed to the Secretaries of the Lichfield Architectural Society, 1843, William Salt Library, Stafford.

²⁴ Besides his main outlets in the mentioned organs, Petit also gave lectures to regional societies, including Oxford, Lichfield, Northampton, St Alban's and Wrexham, some of which were published. The total is probably over 50.

he presumably painted with that in mind. It became bigger and bolder. Within his travels the UK, France, and Italy were covered most frequently. By 1854 he had “noticed upwards of 300 churches in France”²⁵ (Petit, 1890), and many will have multiple drawings either on separate occasions or on the same visit. But he also continued to visit the Low Countries, Germany and east to Prague, Switzerland and Ireland; later he visited Spain, Greece, Constantinople, Syria (including Jerusalem) and Egypt. All these locations contributed watercolours to his posthumous exhibition²⁶.

His painting style continued to evolve. From the mid 1840s around half his works were architectural sketches sometimes with limited sky, foreground and background. His ruins in particular, perhaps because of their nature, convey the power of this style, and the ‘savagery’ of medieval Gothic in a way that Ruskin might have recognised (pl. 17) (Ruskin, 2025)²⁷. Yet, during a long stay in Torquay, in 1848, Petit concentrates on developing his art of shipping and of rock landscapes, showing a capability and forward looking style far distant from that of architectural studies (pl. 18 and 19).

The architectural sketches resumed, in volume, in 1850. Oblique references to himself as artist, such as appear in *Remarks*, continue throughout his writings²⁸. *Architectural Studies in France (FA)*, his second major work appeared in 1854. PH Delamotte had collaborated with him from 1846 onwards, by producing some illustrations for his articles, and now also contributed 44 of the 210 original drawings for *FA*, although the rest were by Petit. The ones used as the basis for illustrations in this book were undertaken from 1850–52, from folios labeled L through to Q. Many of these can be relatively finished by comparison with other sketches, as this example of Notre Dame at Poitiers shows, with the addition of foreground and people which some sketches lack (pl. 20).

Philip Delamotte used examples of Petit, alongside those of celebrated professional watercolourists, in his book *The Art of Sketching from Nature* published in 1871 (Delamotte, 2023):

“...it must be remembered that [Petit’s] object was the collecting of a large number of subjects for the purpose of having them before him when writing; and those who know his writings will remember how much stress he lays upon the beauty of architectural proportion and picturesqueness of the subject; and I may add, that all his early sketch-books prove that he thoroughly understood all the minutest detail both in architecture and shipping, for many of these books contain most beautiful and highly finished details”²⁹.

²⁵ Rev J L Petit, *Architectural Studies in France*, 1854, Ch 2, p 12.

²⁶ *Catalogue of 19th Architectural exhibition Society*, op. cit.

²⁷ Ruskin praised Prout as uniquely capturing the spirit of Gothic architecture in *Modern Painters* – a spirit that in 1853 he defined in *The Nature of Gothic in Stones of Venice* (vol. 2); the most important and first listed characteristic being ‘savagery’. I have not seen any comment by Ruskin directly about Petit.

²⁸ Rev. J. L. Petit, *Remarks*, op cit, for example Vol. II, p. 191 ‘independently of this magnificent structure, the old houses in the streets of Limburg would probably detain the artist for a day or two...’.

²⁹ Mr. P. H. Delamotte, *The Art of Sketching from Nature*, Bell and Daldy, London 1871, ch. 1, p. 8. Delamotte at this time was Professor of Drawing at Kings College and King’s College School. He includes examples of Varley, Prout, DeWint, Girtin, Constable, Cooke, Thomas, Birket Foster; and several of Petit. However since they had been collaborators since 1846, this is not necessarily an objective assessment.

While Delamotte and others did some woodcuts for his publications, Petit also continued to prepare many. These are in the form of detailed ink drawings ready for woodcut engraving or anastatical reproduction – an early form of copying which he used for some illustrations in *FA*. Many of Petit’s illustrations ended up with the publishers. Two albums of contain most of the pen and ink drawings used for *Remarks*. Over 150 illustrations for his *AJ* articles were given to the *AI*, which was noteworthy³⁰. From 1855 Petit participated in the Anastatic Drawing Society and contributed illustrations every year to it and its successor, the *Ilam Anastatic Drawing Society*. In these publications his illustrations stand out³¹. The illustrations in his books and articles were invariably praised, even by his most trenchant critics, for their quality, and quantity. Thus *The Ecclesiologist* in its 1842 review admitted:

*‘A great number of sketches, rough indeed [meaning not measured], but always remarkably correct in perspective, and therefore not generally displeasing to the eye...from their great variety give much value...’*³².

Beautiful landscapes are completed in most years, and Petit experiments artistically when not preoccupied with architectural sketches. Petit continues to develop his impressionistic style for rocks and trees, occasionally paints mines and factories, and he experiments with colour. While in France he deepens the reddish tone (pl. 21). Some watercolours from his trip to Egypt and Syria in 1864–65 differ markedly and echo the freedom and colour of his sketching trip through Europe in preparation for *Remarks* (pl. 22).

A few other characteristics distinguish this later period. The paper is almost exclusively, larger (often 27x37 cm), thicker and rougher. They are usually titled on the reverse instead of on mounts, and dates, and caricature doodles, also appear quite frequently on the backs after 1854. Mostly, but not always, there are also typographed labels on the reverse which reflect their cataloguing at a later date by his sister, the possible significance of which for attribution is discussed below. Nevertheless, apart from the exceptions noted, Petit’s core sketching style continues until his death.

Petit did not participate in watercolour exhibitions by artistic societies, yet he exhibited many watercolours. When he gave lectures and speeches, for example at the annual Architectural Exhibition Society, at Annual Meetings of the Archaeological Institute and similar events they were invariably accompanied by many of his drawings. To accompany his speech, “*On the Picturesque in Architecture*” to the Architectural Exhibition Society in 1863 it was reported that over 100 drawings were shown³³. Besides these events there was the posthumous exhibition of 339 drawings in May–July 1869 referred above which remains his only single artist exhibition, and reports of some being exhibited at, for example Fine Art Society exhibitions later in the century.

Only watercolours are currently known. Albert Hartshorne, in his obituary in *The Builder* in 1869 mentions that a few oils were completed, and some were mentioned in a descendant’s inventory dated 1957, although whether any have survived

³⁰ There is a footnote recording the Committee’s grateful acknowledgement of the gift in every article, in fulsome terms, which does not appear for articles by other authors. In total over 20 gifts of at least 5 drawings each. Petit was known for artistic illustrations.

³¹ These publications are now available online.

³² *The Ecclesiologist*, op. cit., p. 94.

³³ *Evening Standard*. 3rd June 1863, p. 6.

is not clear³⁴.

Petit is not known to have sold, or to have tried to sell, any of his works. When, in the 1850s and 1860s, the AES advertised some of its exhibits for sale, Petit's were not among them³⁵. During his lifetime he gifted a number to his friends and acquaintances, besides the gifts of illustrations to the AI³⁶.

So, the vast majority stayed in his possession and was bequeathed to his family. In his will the bulk are left to the three sisters who lived with him, with 1,000 going to other family members and 120 to friends³⁷. The total number of works left was probably at least 10,000. This might be deduced from the number of albums catalogued in later years, or by his work-rate of 1 a day, sometimes more, over 35 years, but allowing for long breaks for preparing his writing and speeches. His work-rate is seen by a few series of drawings that have stayed together and where the dates are given on the back. A good example of such a series is in the National Library of Wales recording the building of the Chapel at Caerdeon during several months of 1861 and 1862³⁸.

The majority, around 9,000, stayed intact in one family line until being sold in large quantities, through auctions at Sotheby's Billingshurst from 1983 to 1999, and directly to one dealer³⁹. This would not help the appreciation of any artist's work, but in Petit's case the situation has been worsened by two aspects: the fact that all of his work was kept and none pruned during his lifetime; and the confusion with other family members' drawings. This needs some explanation.

Petit had 7 sisters, 6 of whom survived him and 5 of these are known to have painted⁴⁰. In addition his wife appears to have been accompanied for many years by her sister, Amelia Reid, who also painted⁴¹.

Of these, Miss (Emma) Petit and Amelia Reid can be shown to have participated in his illustrations and the artwork for the illustrations, primarily Miss Petit. This family support is most clearly visible in the paper "*Remarks on Sherborn Minster*" in the *Proceedings of the Archaeological Institute* from their annual meeting held in Bristol in 1851. The report acknowledges that illustrations are from drawings by Miss Petit, as well as Petit himself, but 'Miss Reid del' is also visible on two of the illustrations⁴².

³⁴ A. Hartshorne, *The Builder*, op cit. Oils were mentioned in a descendant's inventory from 1957, but these have not yet been traced.

³⁵ *AES Catalogues 1855–1870*, National Art Library, op. cit.

³⁶ Augustus Hare received one when they sketched together in France, Augustus Hare, *Story of My Life*, vol. 1, pp. 611.

³⁷ Codicil dated 1864 to Rev. J. L. Petit's will, *Central Register of Probate Records*.

³⁸ National Library of Wales. In addition to the two catalogue numbers of groups of watercolours by Petit, there is also an album of pencil sketches which is of very doubtful attribution and which is being reviewed.

³⁹ Confirmed by those involved. Estimates of totals sold in each channel are not precise, around 3-5,000 each, possibly accounting for the entire amount after deductions from damage due to poor storage conditions, and additions of many paintings by Petit's circle.

⁴⁰ Works by Harriet Salt are in the William Salt Library. Works initialed by Emma, Louisa, Mary and Maria are in the Samuel Johnson Museum album, described in text. Signed works by Elizabeth Petit are recorded by a dealer.

⁴¹ In his will Petit bequeaths sketches to his wife to be selected by Miss Reid, and some to Miss Reid herself. Newspaper reports from Cheltenham where she was living, in November 1888, describe a theft of 107 watercolours from her collection of her and her brother-in-law's drawings.

In other articles Petit also acknowledges that an illustration is taken from a drawing 'by Miss Petit', the first of these is dated 1846 (Petit, 1846)⁴³. In the *Proceedings* of the AI annual meeting at Lincoln the thanks for the gift of illustrations is differently worded '...from drawings prepared under the special direction of Mr. Petit', though it is not clearly stated to whom this refers. Miss Petit accompanied JLP on many of his travels, including to the Middle East in 1865, as did other family members on other occasions⁴⁴. Miss Petit also prepared the posthumous publications in the *Archaeological Journal*. So, Miss (Emma) Petit was clearly his closest collaborator, but from at least 1846 Miss Petit and other family members were regularly painting with him.

An album that once belonged to Miss Petit survives in the Samuel Johnson Museum in Lichfield and there different drawings bear different initials on the mounting paper: MKP later MKJ (Maria Jelf, nee Petit, his youngest sister), and EP being more common; Mary Chetwynd (nee Petit), and LP (Louisa, either his wife, or the sister who died in 1846) less so, alongside a dozen or so with the initials JLP. Separately a few drawings signed by Elizabeth, his fourth sister, have been seen. Occasionally one of his sisters paints the same view on the same day as Petit, and a direct comparison can be made.

Concerning Emma Petit, it is possible to characterize her work as much weaker architecturally, while attempting the same style (pl. 23-24). MKJ's work shows softer characteristics and less architectural subject matter. Both are more colourful, especially in sky, during the period when Petit himself ignored such luxuries. Where pictures are dated on the back some small differences in handwriting can be seen.

The total number of Petits were reduced considerably by damage. Those witnessing the auctions have estimated up to 40%. But the numbers were supplemented by a similar quantity of 'circle' drawings.

A first approximation is that those pictures with the typographed back labels mentioned are Petit's and the rest are others' work. The typographic labels on the back of his work start around 1847⁴⁵. They organize a significant part of his work in albums of around 100 works designated by a letter of the alphabet and a number for the work. The album letters run sequentially until 'Z' is reached in 1855. In 1856 they used '1856 1', '2', etc.; and then from 1857 settled on '1857 A', B etc. and so on for each year. There is an 1863-4 album and albums labeled simply Egypt and Syria from 1864 and 1865. Other cataloguing systems existed for members of the circle (for example '1863-4' in a red stencil). The labeling seems to be a good but not foolproof guide to authorship in that most later pictures without labels appear to be of different hands, such as pl. 25. However, numbers of later Petits do also exist without labels, and a few with the right labels do not appear to be his, perhaps

⁴² *Transactions of the Archaeological Institute*, 1851, The Rev. J. L. Petit, *Remarks on Sherborne Minster*, inscriptions to drawings.

⁴³ Rev. J. L. Petit, *Ecclesiastical Antiquities in the Isle of Man*, A.J. vol. 3. PH Delamotte makes his first appearance here too. Miss Petit's drawings are also used occasionally in later articles.

⁴⁴ Hare, *op. cit.*, pp. 611-612, reports painting with Petit, Miss Emma Petit, and Miss Salt his niece while in France.

⁴⁵ A picture of Newhaven Church, Sussex which was used for an *AJ* article on churches in Sussex in 1849 has label E17, which would imply the 'A' album would have been started in around 1847. For the time being this can serve as the starting point. Perhaps labels dateable a few years earlier will emerge.

reflecting confusion in sorting them correctly after they returned. Side by side, however, Petit's artistic quality stands out.

Among 9 dealers who held stock in 2016, 7 included a significant proportion of examples which I would clearly attribute to one or other of the family because of their style, labeling and handwriting, Yet all were attributed to JLP. Even a few with the initials of a sister on the mounting paper were similarly mis-attributed. JLP's surviving work anyway includes rough sketches, but the damage to his reputation is compounded by some very poor paintings by his family. In one recent case a painting with a verso date well after his death was auctioned as by Rev. J. L. Petit⁴⁶.

Some of Petit's drawings are in public collections. A small group of 25 early watercolours are with the Staffordshire County. A large bequest of an album and 50 watercolours was given to the National Library of Wales. An album from 1840 is in Southampton University Hartley Archives. There is Emma Petit's album held by the Samuel Johnson Museum at Lichfield, and a couple of pictures at the Victoria and Albert Museum, London.

These then are the main facts known about Petit's artistic work. Although there are questions left unanswered at this stage, nevertheless on the basis of the above there is a clear break in his work around 1843: Early drawings, until around 1843, perhaps 35% of the total, and the later drawings, sketches, and illustrations from 1843 to 1868;

Pre-1843. The early paintings tend to be smaller, on thinner paper, and without typographed labels on the reverse. It is relatively rare to see ones that look like his sisters' work and where the attribution is either unclear, or clearly not Petit. The style changes quite considerably in this period especially the colour from dark to quite colourful.

After 1843. There is a clear break in the style of his work around 1844. In the later drawings, the first obvious point to notice is that the palette changes and a terracotta reddish colour comes to predominate, also the paper is larger and thicker. Within this period from the mid-1840s onwards one finds Petit's most experimental landscapes, marine and rock studies.

To sum up, it is now possible to understand the ways in which Petit is significant as a British mid-19th Century watercolourist.

Firstly it is clear that he must be one of the greatest historical artists of European churches, if not claiming to be the greatest. Not so much by volume, but by the range across Europe, capturing small parish churches in obscure villages as well as Cathedrals. Often these will be the only surviving record of their subject. Most importantly Petit captured the character of the location not simply a plan, as other prolific draughtsmen did. Petit's distinctive, less contrived compositions, his palette and style aim specifically to communicate the majesty and solemnity of church architecture, his abiding passion. '...to encourage a true appreciation of the relics bequeathed to us, as indications of the spirit, character, and genius, of a former age'⁴⁷.

Secondly, although not large in number, Petit's pictures of the industrial landscape in Britain during the 1830s to 1860 are unique as a body of work. There are plenty of other artists who captured one or two examples, but none on the scale and purpose of Petit.

⁴⁶ Keys Auctioneers, Norwich, *Antiques and Interiors, with Pictures*, August 22, 2016 (Lot 451). Description: 'REV JOHN LOUIS PETIT, two watercolours, inscribed verso "S-Provins, August 19th 1877" and "Bougival, Versailles", 10"×15½" and 11½"×9½", unframed (2)'.

⁴⁷ Rev. J. L. Petit, *Tong Church, Salop* in A.J. Vol. 2, end paragraph.

Thirdly, his impressionistic style stands out. David Cox and Turner painted rough watercolours at the end of their careers but even they limited their approach to a few subjects. Petit's appears to have anticipated modern developments in France by 20 years, and in the case of his rock studies, or colour experimentation, by 40 years or more.

Does Petit stand up alongside the better known watercolourists of the day? "There has been nothing like this in the field of British art for a long time – the rediscovery of a more or less completely forgotten master. Petit is a prophet of Impressionism, a true 'painter of modern life', whose work reaches the highest peaks of innovation and virtuosity, worthy of comparison with that even of Turner. High praise, but not too high"⁴⁸. And, to paraphrase Petit's own words ... Little as the hasty critic may be struck by this artist, the careful observer will find as much to reward his trouble as with artists much more renowned for the beauty and magnificence of their works⁴⁹ (Graham-Dixon, 2022). Readers may judge for themselves.

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⁴⁸ Andrew Graham-Dixon, quoted from *The J.L. Petit Series. 2. Impressions of Industry* (RPS Publications, 2025). P. 2.

⁴⁹ This seems to be a popular turn of phrase with Petit, and sums up his modest but persistent approach to putting across his point of view. This particular version 'On the whole, little as the hasty traveller may be struck by the ecclesiastical features of this county, the careful observer will find as much to reward his trouble as in districts more renowned for the beauty and magnificence of their structures' refers to the churches in the county of Sussex which he describes in the *Archaeological Journal* article in vol. 6 of 1849, although it is used also on several other occasions in his writings.

Appendix: Petit Article Plates⁵⁰

1. *The Reverend John Louis Petit, 1801-1868; 1860s.* Photograph on paper, 19.5×15.2 cm, reproduced by permission of the Trustees of the William Salt Library, Stafford

2. *Westminster Abbey, from an album dated 1824,* 12×17 cm

3. *Bakewell Church, Derbyshire 24×35 cm*
The spire came down in 1825 and was not replaced until 1839

4. *The Brig, Harwich, 1828-34,* 23.5×14.5 cm

5. *Oude Kirke, Delft, 1828-34.* 10×19 cm.
A different picture of this church was used in *Remarks* (1841)

6. *Canterbury Cathedral, 1832,* 19.5×14 cm. Taken at the start of dismantling of the old Norman northwest tower (to right)

⁵⁰ Images for reference only. All watercolours by J. L. Petit except where stated; in private collections, except where stated.

7. *Stadhuis, Ghent*, early 1830s, 20x14 cm. Private Collection. Described but not illustrated in *Remarks on Church Architecture*. This is taken very near the place from where Prout drew a similar picture, see plate 8

8. *Stadhuis, Ghent* by Samuel Prout (1783-1852) c1823. Plate 1 in *Sketches by Samuel Prout in France, Belgium, Germany, Italy and Switzerland*, ed. Holme (London 1915). One original is in the British Museum

9. *Near Wolverhampton*, c1830-35, 23x29 cm. Probably the Spring Vale works shortly after construction

10. *Near Wolverhampton*, c1830-35, 16x22 cm. The same title suggests this may be a distant view of the same works

11. *Tixall Gateway*, c 1835, 27x23 cm. Watercolour copied for the illustration, shown adjacent, from p. 24, vol. 1 of *Remarks on Church Architecture*

12. *St. Mary's Stafford*, pre-1841, 19×25 cm. This church was renovated by Gilbert Scott starting in 1841; the renovation planned, among other changes, to give a sloping roof to the south transept (shown on right with flat roof here) and this was vigorously opposed by Petit

13. *Ashbourne Church*, c 1838, 32×23 cm. Probably drawn on the same tour of Derbyshire as the landscapes of March-May 1838, see plate 12

14. *Field near Norbury*, May 1838, dated on mount, 29×23 cm. Private Collection

15. *Norrey Church*, near Caen, c 1839-40, 23×21 cm. Watercolour copied for the illustration facing page 162, in Vol. 1 of *Remarks*. 'an exquisite specimen of Early Complete Gothic...and of more elegant proportions than I remember to have seen in France'

16. *Roman remains, Nr Nice*, c 1839-40, 16×24 cm

17. *Whitby Abbey*, c 1845, 34×26 cm. Savage Gothic

18. *Torquay* c 1848, 24×30 cm. The rocky island called Lead Stone, with Thatcher Rock in the distance. With but a few brush strokes Petit captures the weight and character of the rock

19. *Torquay* c 1848, 24×30 cm. Not the normal romantic view of fishing, Petit conveys the lonely, rough life. Monet would paint an almost identical composition 18 years later

20. *Notre Dame, Poitiers* c 1851-53, 21×28 cm. Watercolour copied for the illustration in *Architectural Studies in France*, 1854, opposite p. 104 'The front is well known by engravings; I, however, give my rough sketch of it because it enables me to point out some peculiar features in Poitevin architecture'

21. *Near Pau, Southern France*, 1859, 27×37 cm. *A fierce red palette seems to intentionally escape from traditional pretty landscapes in green and blue*

22. *Absalom's Tomb*, near Jerusalem, May 10th 1865, dated on reverse, 37×21 cm. An unusually colourful interlude. Copied for illustration in the Ilam Anastatic Drawing Society Collection for 1866 p. 152

23. *Freybourg*, 26th September 1856,
27×37 cm. By JLP.

24. *Freybourg*, 26th September 1856,
27×37 cm. By Emma Gentile Petit